

**БИЗНЕС-МЫШЛЕНИЕ: ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЕ,
СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ**

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Abstract

This article shows the methods of formation and development of human business thinking, entrepreneurial abilities in accordance with the laws of supply and demand in a socio-philosophical manner and from scientific and theoretical competence. At the same time, the importance of creating material and spiritual resources, its impact on the socio-economic system, as well as increasing the knowledge of the emergence of business thinking in the minds of people as directions for the implementation of these actions were highlighted.

Keywords: philosophy, business, development, thinking, entrepreneurship, activity, production, development and prosperity.

In the minds of those who lived in ancient times, there are historical roots that are characteristic of the philosophy of entrepreneurship, which arose as a science that studies the General Laws of the origin, formation and development of entrepreneurship, based on the emergence of business thinking. The concept of "historical root" in a broad sense refers to all aspects of all things and phenomena that exist today, located in historical space and time, and in a narrow sense, to the place occupied by certain entities in historical space and time of things and phenomena aimed at cognition and transformation".

Accordingly, the historical roots of the philosophy of entrepreneurship are a whole system of labor activities based on Business thinking, which has long been inherited from ancestors to descendants, focused on the satisfaction of the needs and interests of themselves and others, by factor, in order to earn more income from the production of Agriculture, Livestock, handicrafts.

From the period of the initial emergence of entrepreneurship, which is based on the development of business thinking in people to the present day, it is a painstaking work that requires the implementation with the participation of specialists in various fields - ancient scientists, Orientalists, historians and philosophers, that is, their coverage based on the study of many sources, in particular, archaeological, Numismatic, handwriting, archival After all, therefore, in this study, first of all, attention is paid to the study of those aspects that form its ontological basis - existing as a material value.

Labor activity, based on the formation of the initial business thinking of ancient people, necessitated their entrepreneurial conduct. More precisely, although entrepreneurial activity, based on the levels of business thinking of the ancient people, is closely linked to the garchand geographical environment, natural resources and economic life, however, this process has experienced situations such as progress and prosperity, degradation and stagnation, persecution and liquidation, revitalization and development, the prospects of which have always been reflected in the political processes taking place, it has been directly related to the nature of trade relations established with other countries and peoples. So, all this philosophically requires a gradual study of the region within the framework of its entire historical development, with the identification of its causes and factors.

This is what is known from the history of the development of society, since the day of the emergence of mankind, it has always been active in relation to the environment that surrounds it in order to save its life. And this is a recognized, true, from the quality of an argument that does not require proof. Therefore, it is desirable to recognize the course of this process as the continuity of the relations of the "man and the world" of the Uzbek entrepreneurial philosophy, based on the development of business thinking of people, the law of a person's activity with a factor.

The continuity of the relations of "Man and the universe", the factual functioning of a person can be viewed as a set of relationships that are important, necessary, General, relatively stable, with business thinking about the use of donations of nature and society, their reproduction, the transformation of the environment, in order for a person to live life within a natural and social being.

The object of entrepreneurship, which is based on the business thinking of people, is primarily material things, relationships aimed at making more profit and earning through their assimilation. It is natural that the question arises when the root of entrepreneurship arose, which is based on the emergence of business thinking in the minds of those who are the beginning of this relationship.

They insist that the origin of entrepreneurial activity, based on the emergence of business thinking of people in its history, dates back to the "Neolithic Revolution", which occurred in 6-4 millennia BC, that is, 8-6 thousand years ago, and the Eneolithic and Bronze Age that followed. . In the era of "Neolithic Revolution", the first material and partly spiritual sources of conducting entrepreneurial activity based on Business thinking were created, in the

sentence of which it is possible to include: the transition from thermalism to agriculture; making small tools of Labor; the transition to a sedentary lifestyle; the construction of cotton and clay houses; the preservation of goods near the
As a result of the development of business thinking of an ancient "Homo habilis" – a business (authentic) person, by the 6th-5th centuries BC, farm maintenance began to be carried out by the natural type of production, that is, by the natural process of satisfying the vital needs of people, families, among their seeds, all Aldi-Verdi relations began to be realized In this, it is mainly people who have focused on what subject can be used more as a weapon of Labor, objects. Through their business use, those who tried to satisfy their needs and interests. The entrepreneurial activity of people with business thinking of ancient times, based on the natural exchange of goods of a primitive form, continued even in the Eneolithic period.

In addition to their discoveries and inventions, mining and smelting ore, making labor tools from the metal obtained from it; making more elaborate work from metal-made labor tools to the lands; laying irrigation works on the road in farming; expanding arable land to form surplus products and organizing their exchange; building multi-room houses from raw bricks; making pottery charges and with the help of done. As a result, the first division of Labor was separated from agriculture by livestock, which then provided ample opportunities for the second division of labor, that is, the emergence of crafts as a separate sphere. These discoveries and inventions had no doubt served as the initial material and spiritual factor that ensured the emergence of the Cretaceous, on which business thinking was based.

The importance of the trade routes that went through here was significant in the way people who lived in ancient times engaged in entrepreneurial activity on the basis of the formation of business thinking. Communication-to the emergence of trade routes: the natural need of people to contact places rich in other food reserves in order to meet their demands on food; the emergence of the need of people to exchange products according to the need for natural conditions; the migration of the population from one territory to another, sometimes natural, according to socio-economic conditions; it would be more correct to say that the natural state of new places in the minds of people, the emergence of perceptions of their geographical location, as well as the establishment of work on the use of animals by training them for the hand, the discovery of the wheel, etc.

As a result of the formation and development of business thinking in the trade, economic, cultural and spiritual ties of living peoples, the buds of philosophical views on entrepreneurship can be seen: firstly, in the organization of work to open and use trade routes; secondly, in the potential of commodity products developed to engage in trade; thirdly, in the productive use.

The further evolution of its policy, based on Business thinking carried out by the ancient States, is directly related to the emergence, formation and development of the "Great Silk Road". The road operated from the 2nd century BC to the 30s of the 20th century, that is, for almost more than 2000 years, witnessing many historical events in the business chapter. The historical place in the development of philosophical ideas about entrepreneurship, based on the formation of business thinking of the peoples living on the territory of the Great Silk Road, is as follows: firstly, the region is connected with the Mediterranean Sea in the East by China in the West, when it studies the trade relations carried out on the lands; secondly, it can be.

In conclusion, it can be said that the growing business thinking of ancient people, on the other hand, laid the foundation for their involvement in entrepreneurial activities. Entrepreneurship, based on the business thinking of ancient people, in turn, is considered one of the realities that has decided in the material life of society as a social phenomenon of ontological tabait, a gnoseological nature, axeological significance.

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